

thiazole nucleus at C₅. This assumption gains further support from the fact that due to the polar effect of the substituents at C₂ and C₄ of a heterocyclic compound like thiazole, the newly entering bromine atom generally attaches to C₅ (Takeda *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1947- 67, 193) which is free.

The final confirmation of the position of the bromine atom at C₅ come from the following observations. When these bromothiazoles are refluxed for 8 hours with HCl (1:3) and allyl alcohol, the original bromine-free thiazoles are obtained, which are in strict accordance with the observations of Garreau (*Compt. rend.*, 1950, 230, 448).

Fungicidal tests.—For fungicidal assay, the method of Montgomery and Moore (*J. Pomol & Hort. Sci.*, 1938, 15, 253) with slight modification has been used. *Alternaria brassicae* (Berk) has been used as the test fungus. The bromothiazoles completely inhibited the spore germination at a concentration of 50 p.p.m.; at a concentration of 40 p.p.m. the spore germination was only 15-20%. The unbrominated thiazoles inhibited the spore germination at a concentration of 80 p.p.m. The details of the fungicidal tests will be published elsewhere.

Bactericidal tests.—The Redean-Walker serial drop dilution method was used for the comparative antibacterial study. The bactericidal activity was measured in terms of maximum effective dilution (M.E.D.) at 10 minutes' contact. The test organisms were 24 hours' culture of *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The unbrominated thiazoles showed an activity in maximum dilution 1:1000 in case of *E. coli* and 1:8000 in case of *Staph. aureus*, while the brominated ones were active in 1:2000 and 1:20,000 dilutions respectively. The antibacterial data are shown in Table I.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzylidene-acetone Dibromide.—Benzylidene-acetone (4 g.) was dissolved in 30 c.c. of chloroform and stirred for some time. Bromine (5 g.), dissolved in 25 c.c. of chloroform, was added dropwise to above and the mixture was stirred for another hour. Chloroform was then evaporated from the mixture and the solid was collected and kept overnight in a vacuum desiccator. It was crystallised finally from absolute alcohol as white, needle-shaped crystals having a pleasant smell similar to that of Indian *Kkaskhas*, m.p. 122-23°, yield 85%. (Found: C, 39.78; H, 4.16; Br, 51.39. $C_{11}H_{10}OBr_2$ requires C, 39.21; H, 3.26; Br, 52.28 per cent).

The compound is fairly stable at ordinary atmospheric pressure. The bromine atoms in the dibromide are labile as the aqueous extract of the solid affords a yellowish white precipitate of AgBr with AgNO₃.

Anisylidene-acetone Dibromide.—Anisylidene-acetone (4 g.) was brominated in the way described above. The solid crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 107°, yield 65%. (Found: C, 38.53; H, 4.37; Br, 46.71. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2Br_2$ requires C, 39.28; H, 3.57; Br, 47.62 per cent). The solid is very unstable in moist air and gradually loses bromine and becomes pasty. On treatment with water it liberates bromine ion, which is detected by its acidic reaction to litmus and affording a yellowish white precipitate with AgNO₃.

TABLE I

No. of Comp.	4-Aryl-2-aminothiazole. Nature of the aryl group.	M.P.	Yield.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.		M.P.	75% Yield.	% Bromine.			
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.		
1	C ₆ H ₅	153-54°	80%	15.13	15.90	18.18	18.18	103°	75%	12.13	12.55	31.83	31.37
2	(p) CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	123-24°	85	14.23	14.74	16.35	16.84	106°	65	11.35	11.89	30.15	27.74
3	(p) C ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄	107-108°	82	13.84	13.72	15.19	15.68	112°	68	12.10	11.30	29.11	28.27
4	(3-4)(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	135-36°	75	13.03	13.72	14.84	15.66	107°	78	10.85	11.30	28.29	28.27
5	(2-5)(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	177-78°	78	12.97	13.72	15.79	15.68	189°	76	10.39	11.30	28.93	28.27
6	p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	204-205°	87	13.62	13.59	15.15	15.53	152°	60	11.69	11.22	28.75	28.07
7	p-C ₂ H ₅ O.C ₆ H ₄	230-31°	85	12.17	12.73	14.73	14.54	98°	66	11.67	10.70	25.89	26.75
8	o-OH.C ₆ H ₄	119-40°	82	13.93	14.58	15.97	16.66	221°	63	10.98	11.80	28.76	29.52
9	p-OH.C ₆ H ₄	128-99°	78	14.01	14.58	16.10	16.66	235°	65	11.30	11.80	30.13	29.52
10	p-Br.C ₆ H ₄	176-77°	68	10.13	10.98	11.92	12.55	192°	78	10.31	9.58	48.16	47.90
11	m-NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	170-71°	71	22.96	21.98	15.98	16.75	207°	66	12.31	11.85	30.33	29.63
12	p-NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	174-75°	82	21.13	21.98	15.93	16.75	203°	72	11.23	11.85	28.73	29.63
13	o-C ₁₀ H ₇	130-31°	81	12.74	12.39	14.76	14.16	111°	75	9.89	10.49	26.88	26.23
14	p-C ₁₀ H ₇	150-51°	85	12.67	12.39	14.01	14.16	168°	78	11.12	10.49	25.83	26.23
15	2-C ₂ H ₅ S(2-Thienyl)	107-108°	65	15.87	15.38	34.90	35.16	217°	61	24.95	24.52	30.91	30.65
16	C ₆ H ₅ .CF ₃ .CH ₂	90-91°	65	13.13	13.72	15.97	15.68	201°	70	11.89	11.30	28.85	28.27
17	CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ .CH ₂	97-98°	88	10.98	11.92	13.01	13.68	197(d)	85	10.93	10.22	26.13	25.55

TABLE II

Antibacterial activity of bromothiazoles.

No. of comp. (vide Table I).	M. E. D. E. Coli.	No. of comp. (vide Table I)	M. E. D. Staph. aureus.	No. of comp. (vide Table I)	M. E. D. Staph. aureus.	M. E. D.	
						E. Coli.	Staph. aureus.
1	1:2,000	8	1:5,000	14	1:15,000	1:2,000	1:10,000
2	1:2,000	9	1:10,000	15	1:20,000	1:2,000	1:15,000
3	1:2,000	10	1:10,000	16	1:20,000	1:2,000	1:15,000
4	1:1,000	11	1:2,000	17	1:10,000	1:2,000	1:15,000
5	1:1,000	12	1:10,000	18	1:10,000	1:2,000	1:5,000
6	1:1,000	13	1:2,000	19	1:10,000	1:1,000	1:4,000
7	1:1,000						

4-(β -Phenylethyl)-2-aminothiazole.—A mixture of benzylidene-acetone dibromide (3 g., 0.01 M), thiourea (0.02 M, 2 g.), iodine (0.01M, 2.5 g.) and dry benzene (25 c.c.) was heated for 30 hours on a steam-bath with reflux condenser. On completion of heating the excess benzene was distilled off. The product was extracted with ether several times to remove unchanged iodine and dibromoketone. The residue was then dissolved in boiling water and filtered hot. The filtrate was cooled to some extent and basified with NH_4OH (conc.). 4-(β Phenylethyl) - 2 - aminothiazole, free from bromine, was separated and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 90-91°, yield 65%. (Found: C, 64.23; H, 6.61; N, 13.13; S, 15.97. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 64.70; H, 5.58; N, 13.72; S, 15.68 per cent).

Bromination of 4-(β Phenylethyl)-2-aminothiazole.—The thiazole (2 g.) was treated with HBr (conc., 3 c.c.) and the hydrobromide salt was dissolved in 25 c.c. of glacial acetic acid; the mixture was stirred and well cooled under ice. Bromine (2 g.), dissolved in 25 c.c. of acetic acid, was added dropwise to above. The whole mixture was then stirred for another hour. The excess acetic acid was distilled under reduced pressure and the residue was treated with water and basified with NH_4OH (conc.). The free amino base liberated was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 201°, yield 70%. (Found: C, 45.78; H, 4.37; Br, 28.85; S, 11.89. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{BrS}$ requires C, 46.64; H, 3.88; Br, 28.27; S 11.30 per cent).

These 5-bromo-2-aminothiazoles have also been condensed with *p*-acetylamino-benzenesulphonyl chloride to form the respective bromosulphathiazoles. These compounds are being tested for their antibacterial, antifungal and antiprotozoal activities.

The author is particularly grateful to Dr. M. K. Rout, Ph.D., Reader in Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack, for his guidance and kind interest in the work

MAHURBHANJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE,
UTTAL UNIVERSITY, CUTTACK-3

Received September 26, 1955.